

EnvDis

D-PhD11-3.1

Responsible Partner: P23 UoS

Contributing partners: PHE

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Project deliverable	D-PhD11-3.1. Presentation of findings Year 3
Project Acronym	PhD11-FBZ4/5- EnvDis
Author	Laura Cristina Gonzalez Villeta
Other contributors	
Due month of the report	November 2022
Actual submission month	November 2022
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: NA
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO-EU <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):

D-PHD11-3.1

Presentation of findings

1. University of Surrey Conferences

1.1. The inaugural UoS Open Research Lecture. Poster presentation. 08/04/22. University of Surrey – Open Research and Reproducibility Society

- Oriented to the wide University community, with a special interest in Open Research praxis.
- Poster presentation of the challenges faced for accessing and downloading data publicly available.
- Open research training.
- Networking.

2. OHEJP-related Conferences

2.1. Anual Scientific Meeting 2022. Poster presentation, round table and 3 minute thesis competition. 09-11/06/2021. Orvieto (It).

- Oriented to the OHEJP consortium as well as open to the general public interested in One Health-related research (Foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial diseases and emerging threats).
- Presentation of the research question (weather as a driver of salmonellosis) and the preliminary results.
- Presentation of PhD project and objectives in a concise and engaging way in 3 minutes.
- Highlights and lessons learned in the round table.

3. External Conferences

3.1. ONE-EU – One Health conference, EFSA. 21-24/06/2022 Brussels (Be).

one **Investigating the role of air temperature as a key driver of salmonellosis: a comparison of two different approaches**

Lara O. Gonzalez-Vizita¹, Alastair Cook¹, Gabriela Fenton¹, Emma Gillingham¹, Theo Karanliou¹, Gordon Nichols¹, Joaquin M. Prada¹, Giovanni Lo Baccaro¹

Introduction

Salmonella is the first agent involved in foodborne outbreaks in Europe. The reported cases reveal a seasonal pattern that points to the importance of the environment as a **potential** predictor. We are exploring the role of weather as a key driver of salmonellosis in humans by assessing its link based on:

- bacterial response in food (method 1: process-driven)
- empirical association between human cases and weather (method 2: data-driven)

Methodology

1. Mathematical estimation of the expected number of human cases based on a Poisson process, which reflects ingestion of food (veg and chicken) contaminated with Salmonella. The rate of infection is assumed to be proportional to the temperature-driven bacterial growth in relevant food and using historical temperatures.
2. Statistical approach where disease records and their spatiotemporal linkage to temperature (long, monthly first-time lags) are used to estimate the probability of finding a case conditional to a range of weather conditions.

Results

A good agreement between the predicted and observed incidence curves was found for England and Wales after simulating the incidence of salmonellosis (Fig. 2). Fig. 2 shows the estimated probability of infection calculated in the population of a defined area with a clear signal is captured with the weather variables considered.

Our work confirms:

- temperature and eggs as relevant factors involved in the temporal patterns of salmonellosis incidence (Fig. 1)
- higher influence in cases for outbreaks in 18-19 weeks AND temperature for 12-13 (Fig. 3)

Conclusions

- Solid proof of the multi-environmental factors that influence salmonellosis transmission is important to tackle these disease events, especially in the framework of **global warming**.
- Climate-environment-protection connection could be used to better understand observed events: temporal patterns and disease case incidence predictions.

Acknowledgments

This project is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. It has received grant funding from Zoonosis and the European Union's Horizon 2020 Grant No. 773830, as well as the kind collaboration of the UK Health Security Agency and the MRC/EEA in the framework of Horizon Europe.

Further information

Follow the meeting [PPT summary](#) and [upload final findings](#) (also connect to [Salmonellosis](#))

- Oriented to public health officers and academic audience interested in One Health.
- Presentation of latest findings on the project.
- Networking with One Health practitioners.
- Over 1,000 participants.